

second leaf at vegetative stage (40 d after planting) and the flag leaf at flowering was measured using a portable LI-6000 at near saturated light (above 1000 $\mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$). The hybrid IR62829A / Vajram showed highest Pn values but marginal (positive) and negative heterosis over restorers in light and shade, respectively. Swarna registered higher heterosis (over restorer) in Pn under both light and shade. The combining ability for Pn seems to be better with IR62829A for Vajram and IR58025A for Swarna.

Total dry matter (TDM) and grain yield were highest in the F₁ hybrids of IR62829A and the restorer Vajram. Harvest index was high in IR62829A / Vajram (only in light), whereas Swarna had higher values. The hybrid IR52829A/Vajram showed higher dry matter, yield, and harvest index than the standard check Swarnaprabha.

High positive heterosis for TDM and yield was found in the hybrids of the IR62829A CMS line under shade, whereas under light marginal heterosis was observed for TDM only. The

hybrids of IR58025A CMS line showed negative heterosis for yield and harvest index under both light and shade regimes (except IR58025A/Swarna for TDM under shade). The hybrid IR62829A / Swarna showed high heterosis for TDM and yield under shade; under normal light IR62829A/Vajram recorded higher values for yield and harvest index, but this hybrid showed higher grain yield under both conditions, indicating its agronomic superiority in yield with greater harvest index. ■

Estimation of elongation efficiency in deepwater rice varieties

P. M. Mohapatra and A. R. Panda, Plant Breeding and Genetics Division, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, Orissa, India

When submerged, deepwater rice shows rapid elongation of internode, leaf sheath, and leaf blade, the amount depending on variety. We studied 15 deepwater varieties for their relative elongation efficiency during the 1996 wet season at Cuttack. Three pots with two 37-d-old plants of each variety were submerged in a 110-cm deepwater tank. On the first day, water level was maintained at 40 cm, and on the following day it was raised to 110 cm. The height of plants was recorded before submergence and every 2 d during submergence, up to 10 d. The relative elongation efficiency indices of the varieties were calculated by the formula suggested by Singh (1982):

$$\text{Elongation efficiency index} = \frac{X(N-0) + X(N-2) + X(N-4) + X(N-6) + X(N-8)}{N(\text{Maximum elongation observed})}$$

where X₁, X₂, X₃, X₄, and X₅ stand for actual elongation (in cm) during first, second, third, fourth, and fifth observation, respectively, N is the total span in days (10) from submergence to last observation.

Actual elongation of 15 varieties after submergence for 10 d.

Variety	Actual elongation (cm 48 h ⁻¹)					Total (cm)	Elongation efficiency index
	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅		
Jalamagna	25.8	13.8	11.6	10.8	9.4	71.4	0.70
TCA4	21.8	15.5	12.0	8.5	8.5	66.3	0.65
Jalanidhi	10.2	7.6	22.6	11.1	15.5	67.0	0.52
NDGR410	17.8	20.6	21.1	5.2	2.8	67.5	0.69
Kariawa	16.8	13.4	9.0	16.3	15.3	70.8	0.59
LPR56-49	6.2	6.2	11.8	4.0	7.3	35.5	0.30
TCA282	13.4	13.4	17.0	4.7	5.6	54.1	0.52
TCA269	12.0	8.6	22.6	8.0	7.0	58.2	0.52
Madhukar	9.0	9.8	12.2	8.0	7.1	46.1	0.40
NDGR413	13.0	16.4	13.6	11.0	9.8	63.8	0.57
TCA12	12.6	12.0	16.4	8.5	7.1	56.6	0.52
Chakia 59	8.4	9.4	22.2	4.3	2.6	46.9	0.44
Jalapriya	8.8	6.0	13.6	7.2	5.6	41.2	0.36
Bojaz	12.2	8.4	21.6	2.8	2.3	47.3	0.47
LPR85	4.70	5.1	24.4	5.5	4.5	44.2	0.37

Jalamagna had the highest elongation efficiency index (0.70), followed by NDGR410 (0.69), TCA4 (0.65), and Kariawa (0.59) (see table). The higher indices of the above varieties might be attributed to attainment of maximum rate of elongation at an early stage (higher X₁ values), except for NDGR410, which had consistently high elongation rates up to the third observation (high X₁, X₂, and X₃ values). Most of the varieties attained maximum elongation rate after 6 d of submergence (higher X₃ values) and had comparatively low elongation efficiency indices. The varieties with elongation efficiency indices higher than 0.44 managed to penetrate the water surface while those below 0.44 remained submerged. ■

Histological variation among aromatic rice

L. P. Awasthi, A. K. Sharma, and D. M. Maurya, Genetics and Plant Breeding Department, Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology Kumarganj, Faizabad 224229, Uttar Pradesh, India

Fifteen popular aromatic genotypes were studied to ascertain the variation for histological traits in leaves and shoots. Photomicrographs of the transverse sections of leaves revealed that the cuticle in all genotypes was thin compared with that of the nonaromatic check, Mahsuri. The size

of metaxylem, protoxylem, and phloem elements bundle were highly variable, Large metaxylem (50-60 nm), protoxylem (40-50 nm), and phloem (20-25 nm) were observed in mild aromatic genotypes (Adamchini, Kesar, Lalmati, and T3). They were of medium size in the nonaromatic check and in moderately aromatic genotypes (Kanakjeer, N12, Pusa 33, Sakkar chini A, T3, T9, and Tilak Chandan) and small in strongly aromatic genotypes (Basmati 370, Kalanamak, Kasturi, Phool Chameli A, and Pusa Basmati 1). Most of the genotypes had small- to medium-sized companion cells in the phloem.

Mesophyll cells of Basmati 370, Kalanamak, Kasturi, and Pusa Basmati 1 were extremely swollen, with fewer intercellular spaces than those in the other genotypes. The parenchymatous cells of the midrib were highly enlarged and resembled vesicles. Abnormal thickening of mesophyll and a slight protrusion of cell walls were also observed. Such cells were not so visible in the mildly aromatic genotypes as well as in the nonaromatic check Mahsuri (Fig. 1).

Transverse sections of shoots exhibited little genetic variation for thickness of cuticle, appearance of ground tissue, and pith. However, the number of cell layers in the hypodermis and the degree of lignification were highly variable. Kanakjeer and Pusa Basmati 1 possessed highly lignified hypodermis.

The number of vascular bundles varied greatly. Adamchini had up to 75 bundles and T9 up to 45. In strongly aromatic genotypes (Basmati 370, Kalanamak, Kasturi, and Pusa Basmati 1), normal phloem and xylem elements were replaced by a largely undifferentiated parenchymatous cell mass. Abnormal amounts of xylem tissue were produced with a large number of abnormal sieve elements. On the other hand, mildly aromatic genotypes and the nonaromatic check Mahsuri were free of this histological peculiarity (Fig. 2). ■

1. Photomicrograph of transverse section of leaf. a. Aromatic genotype Basmati 370. b. Nonaromatic genotype Mahsuri.

2. Photomicrograph of transverse section of shoots. a. Aromatic genotype Basmati 370. b. Nonaromatic genotype Mahsuri.

Fertilizer management—*inorganic sources*

Preliminary studies on response of a rice-based crop sequence to S and Zn in temperate Kashmir, India

B. Hasan, S. K. University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology, c/o P. O. Box 706, G. P. O., Srinagar Kashmir 190001, India

This study varied levels and frequencies of S and Zn applications to determine effects on crop yields in a rice - rapeseed cropping pattern. It started in summer 1992, using a rice crop followed by rapeseed until winter 1994 at the university's Shalimar Research Farm (1587 m msl). The soil is an Alfisol (Hapludalf) silty clay loam, pH 6.8, organic C 0.37%, low in available N (alkaline permanganate method), low in available P (Olsen's method), and medium in available K (1 N neutral ammonium acetate method). It con-

tained 9 ppm available S (ammonium acetate-acetic method) and 0.66 mg kg⁻¹ Zn (DTPA extractable).

A randomized block design with four replications was used. The treatments consisted of a control plot (NPK applied at 80-26.2-33.2 kg ha⁻¹), two levels of S (10 and 20 kg ha⁻¹ as calcium sulfate dehydrate), and three levels of Zn (3, 6, and 9 kg ha⁻¹ as zinc oxide). A traditional variety K39 (SK5) of transplanted rice was used. Sulfur and Zn were applied basally along with recommended levels of NPK to each rice crop.

Application of S or Zn with NPK resulted in significant increase in grain yield over the control (see table). During 1992, rice grain yield was maximum (4.02 t ha⁻¹) at 10 kg S ha⁻¹, whereas rapeseed yield was highest (1.26 t ha⁻¹) at 20 kg S ha⁻¹ applied to the previous rice crop. Both S and Zn had significant residual effect on the succeeding crop of rapeseed. This re-